

Simulation of spatial compounding technique using k-wave toolbox

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Abstract — *The reduction of speckle noise and other artifacts inherent to ultrasound imaging and the increase in resolution of the reconstructed images are important features to improve the image signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR). Consequently, this will facilitate the interpretation and assertiveness of medical diagnosis. In this work, we investigated the spatial compound imaging technique aiming to reduce speckle. In this image modality, for different ultrasound beam orientations (deflecting angles), B-mode sub-images are acquired, and then composed into a single image, called spatial compound image. We used K-Wave simulation toolbox for MatLab with a computational phantom (3 spheres in a heterogeneous medium) scanned by a 3.5 MHz 128 element linear transducer. We have observed improvement in both metrics for several conditions.*

Keywords—*Medical ultrasound, Spatial Compound, Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), Contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR).*

I. INTRODUCTION

The ultrasound imaging modality applied as an auxiliary tool for medical diagnosis is one of the most widespread in many applications and clinical examinations in this area, mainly because it is a safe technique, minimally invasive, easy-to-use, enable “real-time” images (despite being a reconstructed, non-instantaneous image, this process can be done quickly enough to be considered a real-time image as long as it has at least 30 frames per second) the equipment is less expensive when compared to equipment of other imaging modalities and yet another great advantage is that ultrasound is not an ionizing radiation [1,2]. With advances in electronic instrumentation such as ever smaller multi-element transducers, the use of ever-faster digital electronics and microprocessors, and the use of digital signal and image processing techniques, tremendous progress was made in the quality of medical ultrasound diagnostic images [1,3].

Spatial compound imaging (SCI) technique uses the stochastic feature of speckle to reduce the grainy appearance of ultrasound images, enabling improvement in the images Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). This ratio is one of the most important metrics for quantitative analyses of ultrasonic images improvement. The major disadvantage of SCI technique is the reduction in the number of frames per second and also the challenges of its clinical application [3-5].

II. THEORY

A. Ultrasonic speckle

Ultrasound images often have spatial characteristics that do not accurately represent the physical structure of the tissue. This is due to artifacts that may originate from many sources and must be identified to avoid misinterpretation of the image,

thus providing useful diagnostic information. The most studied artifact regarding the formation of ultrasonic images is called acoustic speckle. Acoustic speckle is inherent to imaging obtained by systems that make use of coherent sources (such as ultrasound), this artifact originates due to the coherent interference between acoustic waves, which is related to the distance and phase between spreaders that the system is capable to solve [2, 6].

The resolvability of these spreaders has an intrinsic relationship between the pulse length (frequency and number of cycles that make up a pulse) and the distance between the spreaders. In situations where the distance between the spreaders is less than half the wavelength (or the emitted pulse length), it is said that the system cannot resolve the structure, and constructive or destructive interference may occur due to overlap of reflections.

Speckle B-Mode images have a degradation of spatial resolution, grainy aspect even in regions of the same material, reduced contrast resolution and edge definition, making it difficult to detect and identify structures of interest [9, 14-16]. The speckle artifact is known to present in ultrasound images as a deterministic pattern combined with statistical noise. The deterministic nature of speckle derives from the constructive or destructive interference between reflected waves of targets in a given medium and basically depends on the wavelength and speed of sound in that medium. Therefore, the speckle pattern can be repeated when an object is scanned repeatedly under the same aperture conditions, pulse length, deflection angle, and so on [4].

B. Computer simulation of ultrasonic systems

The process of modeling and generation of scattering structures has the purpose of creating reflective interfaces with different acoustic impedances in relation to the environment and in known positions so that physical phenomena can be visualized, such as the reflection of ultrasound waves.

These acoustic spreaders can be modeled as complex variables, where the magnitude corresponds to the reflection coefficient (ie, defines the portion of the incident wave that will be reflected) and the phase refers to the delay introduced to the reflected signal, characterizing the mechanical deformation of the interfaces [7].

It is well established that echoes captured by a transducer can be modeled by convolution between an ultrasonic pulse and a spreader of a given magnitude and phase [7-10].

A simplified process for mathematical and computational modeling of a pulse-echo system is shown in Figure 1, where the transmission circuit generates an electrical stimulus, $g(t)$, which will excite piezoelectric ceramics, which has an electromechanical impulsive response denoted by $h(t)$.

Fig. 1. Block diagram showing the signals in an echo pulse ultrasound system. Signal $g(t)$ is the exciting electrical pulse from the transmission circuit. The signal $p(t)$ is the ultrasonic signal generated by the transducer excited by pulse $g(t)$. Signal $r(t)$ is the RF signal at the input of the receiving circuit that will be processed.

Thus, the transmitted pulse, $p(t)$, which will interact with the medium, can be calculated from the convolution of $g(t)$ and $h(t)$ (the operator $*$ denotes the convolution between the two signals).

When propagating in a medium, the pulse will interact with the spreaders present in that medium, which may be represented by Dirac Delta functions, $\delta(t-t_1)$, where t_1 is the signal's round trip delay.

Thus, the backscattered signals can be obtained from the convolution of the transmitted pulse and the spreaders. This signal must be converted back into an electrical signal, and for this, we convolve with $h(t)$, obtaining the RF signal, $r(t)$, according to Equation 1.

$$r(t) = p(t) * \delta(t-t_1) * h(t) = g(t) * h(t) * \delta(t-t_1) * h(t) \quad (1)$$

The result, $r(t)$, is a complex signal. As we want to work with the signal envelope that is determined by the Hilbert Transform, which generates an analytical RF signal, that is, composed of two components, magnitude and phase, where the phase is neglected for the processing steps [7].

C. Evaluation metrics

Signal-to-Noise Ratio

The signal-to-noise ratio is one of the most commonly used metrics for indicating ultrasound image quality because it provides a means of estimating the accuracy with which a signal is measured, and is defined as the ratio between ultrasound signal intensity and noise present in the image. The higher the resulting value of this division, the better the image quality [11].

The SNR_C (composite signal-to-noise ratio) analysis, calculated from Equation 2, separately evaluates the averages and variances between two regions of interest, for example, an object and a background. As these are two distinct regions, the expected ranges of values for SNR_C will depend on the average amplitudes of the analyzed regions.

$$SNR_C = \frac{\mu_{obj} + \mu_{bg}}{2\sqrt{\sigma_{obj}^2 + \sigma_{bg}^2}} \quad (2)$$

In Equation 2, σ_{obj} e σ_{bg} are, respectively, the variance of the object and background pixel intensity and μ_{obj} and μ_{bg} are, respectively, the average of the object and background pixel intensity.

Contrast-to-Noise Ratio

Although the spatial compound image technique may reduce the contribution of speckle, the major improvements of Contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) are obtained in tissue harmonic images and pulse inversion harmonic images, as well as by the use of contrast agent ultrasound (the last three are not covered in this paper).

CNR analysis provides a mean of estimating the accuracy with which one signal can be discriminated from another signal, and therefore the CNR can also be used as an indicator of image quality.

The CNR_C (composite contrast-noise ratio) analysis, calculated from Equation 3, also separately assesses the mean and variance of pixel intensity between background and object regions [7-11]. As these are two distinct regions, the expected ranges of values for CNR_C will depend on the average amplitudes of these regions.

$$CNR_C = \frac{\mu_{obj} - \mu_{bg}}{2\sqrt{\sigma_{obj}^2 + \sigma_{bg}^2}} \quad (3)$$

In Equation 3, σ_{obj} e σ_{bg} are, respectively, the variance of the object and background pixel intensity and μ_{obj} and μ_{bg} are, respectively, the average of the object and background pixel intensity.

III. METHODS

A. Phantom

It was used the K-Wave toolbox for MATLAB [12] and C++, developed for acoustic and ultrasound simulations in complex medium and realistic mimic tissues [13,14].

The simulation algorithm was performed on a computer with the following characteristics: Intel I7 CPU with 32 Gbytes of data RAM, CUDA GPU board and compatibility to the available toolbox, which reduces the processing time for each simulation.

The simulated phantom was scanned with na aperture of 32 elements from a linear transducer. Each frame is composed of 96 scanlines. The phantom consists of a homogeneous medium with an average density of 1000 kg/m³ and propagation velocity $c = 1540$ m/s. It contains three spherical inserts with higher scatterer density. The insert diameters are 9, 10 and 12 mm (Figure 2). In these regions, the speed of sound propagation, c , varies between 1400 and 1600 m/s and the density varies with c .

Fig. 2. The phantom and the positioning of the simulated transducer (black rectangle indicated) and the three regions of higher density can be seen.

Fig. 3. Can be seen the scattering map before changing grid parameters (left) and after (right).

Simulations were performed for the frequency of 3.5 MHz, each pulse contained 4 cycles at the said central frequency. Data were sampled at 60 MHz. The grid spacing in each direction and the sound propagation speed govern the maximum frequency that the computational grid can support (3.6 MHz). In order to be able to perform simulations with the 3.5 MHz transducer avoiding aliasing, the grid parameters were altered, resulting in a distorted image. Therefore, instead of the image of three spheres, it appears three ellipses (Figure 3). With this modification, the supported frequency of the computational grid reaches 9 MHz.

B. Methodology for spatial compound imaging

To implement the spatial composition technique, simulations were performed with the beam deflection angle varying according to the following angles: $\pm 10^\circ$, $\pm 7.5^\circ$, $\pm 5^\circ$, $\pm 2.5^\circ$, plus normal incidence. The conventional B-mode images are build up following the regular steps for B-mode reconstruction, such as: beamforming, time gain control, band-pass filtering, envelope detection and log compression.

A single image is obtained from the arithmetic mean of the frames (conventional B-mode images obtained with different angles of deflection), but, for this compounding to be made coherently, a frame realignment step is performed before this sum. For a given deflection angle of the beam used (θ), a point represented by (u, v) no raw data space corresponds to (x, y) without real space, and can be used by applying as equations 4 and 5. Only after this realignment can the frame pixels be averaged to obtain a coherent image [5].

$$y = v - u \cdot \sin(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$x = u \cdot \cos(\theta) \quad (5)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The conventional B-mode image can be seen in Figure 4, where the first sphere is designated by the green rectangle, the second sphere by the white rectangle and the third one by the blue rectangle. The image presented in Figure 5 is a spatial compound image obtained with 5 frames.

Fig. 4. B-Mode reconstructed image. Highlighting the phantom regions of the first, second and third spheres, respectively, rectangles in green, white and blue.

Fig. 5. Spatial compounding image obtained with 5 frames.

TABLE I. VALUES OBTAINED FOR SNRC AND CNRC ANALYSIS FOR B-MODE IMAGES AND COMPOUNDING IMAGES WITH 5 FRAMES.

ROI	SNR_C B-Mode	SNR_C Compound Image	CNR_C B- Mode	CNR_C Compound Image
1st sphere	14,73	37,18	7,91	18,85
2nd sphere	13,40	59,25	11,60	43,30
3rd sphere	21,73	15,00	18,61	9,68

With the application of the spatial compound technique, an increase in SNR_C and CNR_C is expected, which did not occur as expected only for the region of the third sphere analyzed, as can be seen in Table I, which is probably associated with the relation between the size of the ROI and background used for the quantitative analysis in relation to the sphere area. It is still possible to qualitatively evaluate the best definition of the edges of the targets and the reduction in grainy appearance that occurs due to the speckle artifact by observing Figure 5 when compared to the Figure 4.

Fig. 6. Spatial compounding image obtained with 9 frames.

TABLE II. VALUES OBTAINED FOR SNR_C AND CNR_C ANALYSIS FOR B-MODE IMAGES AND COMPOUNDING IMAGES WITH 9 FRAMES.

ROI	SNR_C B-Mode	SNR_C Compound Image	CNR_C B-Mode	CNR_C Compound Image
1st sphere	14,73	42,27	7,91	21,43
2nd sphere	13,40	68,46	11,60	48,40
3rd sphere	21,73	21,32	18,61	13,76

By applying the spatial image composition technique, an increase in SNR_C and CNR_C is expected, which can be observed for two of the three regions analyzed, except for the third sphere region, as shown in Table II. It is also possible to qualitatively evaluate the best edge definition and the reduction in grainy appearance that occurs due to the speckle artifact by observing Figure 6 when compared with Figure 4.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, a comparative study between the technique of reconstructing simulated B-Mode images with spatial frame composition (SFC) against the conventional image (reconstructed in Mode-B only) by means of SNR_C and CNR_C evaluation of ROIs was shown. (targets). Qualitative analysis of the images was also performed. The techniques were successfully implemented and the comparative computational study carried out shows that the implementation of optimized processing techniques for image reconstruction, although playing a relevant role in the evaluated aspects, depends greatly on the desired application, such as the depth of the structure of interest. For the 3.5 MHz simulation, considering the evaluated

parameters, among the composition techniques, the best result was obtained for the 9-frame spatial composition technique in B-Mode. However, it has been argued that it is not necessary to use 9 frames to obtain similar results, since there is a large decrease in frame rate, and this makes the image obtained by 5-frame spatial composition more interesting in a lower power scenario. The implementation of the techniques is important to show the difficulties of improving the quality of images made available to the healthcare professional when implemented in commercial equipment. It is expected that the results obtained in this work can be implemented in the Brazilian Ultrasound Platform under construction by the Brazilian Network of Ultrasound Techniques (RBTU) led by UNICAMP.

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